

Perception System in an Autonomous Vehicle: A comprehensive review

¹Vinit Joshi, ²Nupur Avasare, ³Rutwik Bhangale, ⁴Sagar Patel

Mechanical Engineering
Dwarkadas J. Sanghavi College of Engineering
Vile Parle, Mumbai- 400056, India.

Abstract- Autonomous Vehicles are capable of driving on their own and making decisions based on signals received by various sensors that are integrated into the system. Sensors form the key element for receiving information in any driverless car. Autonomous cars can broadly be classified into 6 levels ranging from No Automation where sensors are used as warning systems only to Full Automation where the driver only must give inputs like the route and start the car, all other functions are handled by the car itself including the decision making. This review paper gives a brief description of the working of an Autonomous vehicle, SAE Levels of Automation, and different sensor technology used in autonomous vehicles.

Keywords: Autonomous, sensors, LiDAR, GPS, Radar, IMU.

INTRODUCTION

An autonomous vehicle is a form of smart automotive that primarily uses a mounted smart driving instrument to enable autonomous control. It contributes to a decrease in carbon dioxide emissions, traffic congestion, and auto accidents. The technological model of a self-driving automobile may be divided into four groups: motion control, path planning and decision-making, location and map production, and perception and modeling of the environment. An autonomous automobile may reach its destination safely and on time by detecting its surroundings and choosing the best route without human assistance. As a result, the self-driving car's core technology is environmental awareness. The essential functions of an autonomous vehicle's environmental perception are road detection, road sign recognition, object tracing, pattern detection, and location interpretation. The perception system of an autonomous vehicle must have the desired features which are listed below.

1. Accuracy: to deliver accurate driving environment information to the car.
2. Sturdy: to function regularly and not malfunction easily.
3. Real-time: to avoid time-related stumbling blocks.

In order to attain these qualities, a variety of sensors and reliable fusion algorithms are needed. Based on the combination of sensors, actuators, software, etc. used the vehicles can be broadly classified into different levels of automation.[1]

LITERATURE SURVEY

Our research included a thorough analysis of 29 research articles by eminent authors about the perception system of autonomous vehicles, which has the potential to develop into a blooming field of study in the near future. Autonomous vehicles have been introduced as a result of increased automation and robotics research and development as well as growing public curiosity. Self-driving cars were once only a dream, but they are now a reality.[2][3] Automated cars have the ability to travel independently along a specified route. The sensors and built-in systems that it has are what drives this movement.[4][5]

According to the research, the perception system under development is updated on a regular basis. Autonomous vehicles use GPS, video cameras, ultrasonic sensors, LiDAR, and radar systems.[6] These sensors are used to meticulously gather and examine environmental data. Autonomous vehicles respond in accordance with this recorded data. Further, our literature survey is segregated into three fields namely SAE levels of Automation, working of an autonomous vehicle and its perception system in detail.

SAE Levels of Automation

In 2014, SAE International (Society of Automotive Engineers), an automotive standardization group, proposed a classification system.[7] Rather than vehicle capabilities, this categorization method is focused not only on the level of chauffeur's engagement but also on awareness required. On September 30, 2016, the SAE changed the traditional classification for levels of automation for driverless cars. This technical classification defines these mutually exclusive degrees of driving automation and develops a standardized method for concepts linked to cars with automated systems.[8][9]

	Automated System	Human Driver	STEERING & ACCELERATION/ DECELERATION	MONITORING OF DRIVING ENVIRONMENT	CONTROL WHEN AUTOMATION FAILS	OPERATIONAL DESIGN DOMAIN
0 NO AUTOMATION		Human Driver	Human Driver	Human Driver	Human Driver	LIMITED
1 DRIVER ASSISTANCE	Automated System	Human Driver	Human Driver	Human Driver	Human Driver	LIMITED
2 PARTIAL AUTOMATION	Automated System	Human Driver	Automated System	Human Driver	Human Driver	LIMITED
3 CONDITIONAL AUTOMATION	Automated System	Human Driver	Automated System	Automated System	Human Driver	LIMITED
4 HIGH AUTOMATION	Automated System	Human Driver	Automated System	Automated System	Automated System	LIMITED
5 FULL AUTOMATION	Automated System	Human Driver	Automated System	Automated System	Automated System	UNLIMITED

Figure 1: SAE Levels of Automation

The levels indicated above are crucial since they establish fundamental requirements for a vehicle's technical sophistication.[10]

Working of Autonomous Cars

To execute AI software, autonomous cars require a combination of sensors, actuators, complicated algorithms, machine learning systems, and advanced computing. The driver just needs to enter the end destination or route, and the car will not only construct but also maintain a map of its periphery by using several sensors attached to the autonomous car. A Light Detection & Ranging (LiDAR) sensor is used to scan the environment and produce graphical 3D pictures of the present environment. As a result, it is installed on the roof and can spin 360 degrees.[11] Radio Detection and Ranging (RADAR) sensors located at the front and rear calculate the distance between various objects in the path.[12] Data is also collected on both the sides of the vehicle which assists in tracking its relative location in compliance with a 3D map. All the sensors used are linked to AI software and can receive data from Google Street View and video cameras. Google Maps is linked for obtaining preliminary information on traffic warnings, exits, freeways, landmarks, and so on. The AI software can make decisions as well as handle the steering, throttle, and braking system. An override function is also offered, allowing humans to take control as and when needed. Data acquired from neighboring cars, particularly information about traffic congestion and safety issues, may effectively help vehicles.[13][14] The vehicle's perception system is responsible for producing an internal representation of the exterior environment using a multisensory system. The decision-making system, on the other hand, oversees selecting the best potential route when the driver enters the ultimate destination. It bases its decisions on a variety of elements such as traffic, safety, comfort, and an internal depiction of the current environment.

Figure 2: Working of an Autonomous Vehicle

Perception System

A sensor is a device capable of perceiving its surroundings as well as changes in external stimuli and converting them into electrical output signals that can be measured and so quantified. They can be broadly categorized into two categories based on the elements to be sensed, namely proprioceptive and exteroceptive sensors. The proprioceptive sensors can sense and measure the status of the vehicle, such as wheel position, speed, battery charge, and so on, whereas the exteroceptive sensors can sense the condition of the external surroundings, such as the distance between obstacles, light intensity, and sound amplitude. Inertial measurement units (IMUs), gyroscopes, magnetometers, and locators are proprioceptive units, and cameras, ultrasonic sensors, LiDAR, and RADAR are exteroceptive units. These sensors are a part of two classifications: active and passive sensors. Active sensors emit energy in the form of a wave and search for objects based on the information received. RADAR, for example, uses the concept of reflection of radio waves upon incidence with reflective objects along the same path. Vision cameras are an example of passive sensors which perceive their surroundings and collect data without producing any waves. Autonomous sensors are critical in autonomous driving because they enable automobiles to monitor their surroundings, detect impending problems, and plan safe routes.[14]

To identify the surrounding, the autonomous car uses a laser, LiDAR, RADAR, Odometer, and computer vision. Autonomous cars are incorporated with control systems that can sense and interpret data to distinguish between various objects such as a road closure, or maybe another car which is essential to plan a route to a specific location. The technologies used in the Perception system include numerous systems as given below.

Ultrasonic Sensor

A dependable system that indicates the presence of potential obstacles in the path of the vehicle that can help to reduce accidents is an Ultrasonic Sensor. Ultrasonic Sensors are categorized into two different types - namely short-range ultrasound and the other being long-distance ultrasound. The vehicle is equipped with ultrasonic short-range sensors at the front and rear to gauge the various obstacles in the path. Another type of ultrasonic sensor located at the side of the vehicle helps to determine the distance between obstacles.[1] An array of ultrasonic sensors was used to identify the type of vehicle environmental target. For dynamic tracking, it generated unscented Kalman filtering algorithms. This method enabled real-time object detection and discrimination.[15] The characteristics of the Ultra Sonic sensors are short wavelength, low diffraction, and high frequency. The pros of using the Ultrasonic sensor include it gives good directivity. Therefore, it is used in reverse parking applications. But there are a few drawbacks of using the Ultrasonic sensor which include limited frequency range and low sensitivity.[16]

LiDAR

LiDAR sensors identify things using a pulsed laser. LiDAR instrument consists of a laser beam, data collection unit and GPS unit. The most typical model selection criteria are laser channels, field of view, and resolution of vertical beams. LiDAR Installation is crucial as it determines its efficient working and data collection; a successful installation strategy can be obtained by considering both the specifications of the chosen model and the end goal to be achieved. Laser channels can be increased for improved coverage and precision, but it usually results in more expenditure.[17][18]

Methodology of LiDAR

LIDAR technology is employed in automated cars to distinguish objects in their immediate vicinity. LIDAR provides additional sensing devices beyond what standard sensors can provide. 3D profiles of the vehicles are typically created from the cloud points, and they can be used to extract valuable features for classification.[19]

Data Pre-processing of LiDAR

Velodyne manufactured a VLP type LiDAR unit to collect information about the surroundings. This sensor can have up to 16 laser beams and is capable of complete rotation providing a 30-degree view angle. The LiDAR unit is set at a particular frequency which ensures the generation of a large dataset of cloud points. Depending on the application, the sensor is installed in multiple scanning modes.[20] It will cover a maximum of 50 meters in the direction of the path if installed horizontally, but it will not generate a dense cluster of dots to show every vehicle detected. It covers less than 3.5 meters of the route longitudinally in a vertical configuration and gives more dense points per car. This range can accommodate most passenger vehicles, but vehicles longer than 3.5 meters will not. To build the full 3D or 2D profiles of vehicles, many scans or frames must be integrated. The LiDAR is set up in a vertical configuration for this study. Since cars only travel on the extreme end lane at the information collection location, the reflected dots or points from other objects will be removed from the large dataset. To reduce these redundant data points, thresholds are set. All analyses are conducted using a subset of data from vehicles going in the right lane.

Figure 3: Flowchart of LiDAR Data Process

Speed Estimation of LiDAR

As we know, many frames need to be combined to create a complete car profile, and this is only possible by knowing the car's velocity. The vehicle's velocity can be estimated using the sampling time of the vehicle entering the scan area of each beam and the previous two frames. [20] Similarly, after the vehicle exits the detection zone of the sensor, the final two frames may be utilized to calculate its speed again. Indeed, information from these frames may be used to estimate speed in the very same way until the car does not cover the whole set of not more than sixteen beams in continuous frames. These speeds are then averaged speed to determine the vehicle's average constant speed.

GPS

GPS or Global Positioning System is a fascinating technology that includes instantaneous data which is gathered from satellites. With real-time information, it can calculate longitude, speed and latitude to aid navigation. The aim of Autonomous vehicles is to develop a driverless car model that can navigate through known data points without human intervention. The aim is to show that the navigation of the junction GPS fix can be achieved with a low-cost IMU. The investigation of fused sensors is an area of interest for many researchers. [21][22]

RADAR

Radar detects the environment by measuring the time, angle and intensity of weak radio waves, which have longer wavelengths than lidar. Radar has lower resolution and accuracy than lidar, but is more resistant to occlusions. Radar is mounted on the vehicle for stability. Radar has a wide measuring range. Due to the different wavelengths of the electromagnetic waves, LiDAR and RADAR have additional features. Therefore, proper sensor coupling considering the characteristics of two sensors can improve the expected results.[23]

Figure 4: Schematic Block Diagram of an FMCW RADAR[24]

The diagram above shows a schematic block diagram of an FMCW radar. Radar can detect multiple objects and their distance by performing Fast Fourier Transform on the IF signal and identifying the sound corresponding to each object. Calculate the relative velocity of an object by comparing its Doppler shift. [25]

Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU)

IMU is an electronic device that can monitor and report on the vehicle's orientation, velocity, forces, and so on. A typical IMU consists of accelerometers which are used to measure forces and acceleration of the vehicle, gyroscopes for measuring orientation and monitoring angular velocity, and magnetometers as a passive sensing technology to detect changes in the ambient magnetic field surrounding the vehicle.[26] IMU data provides crucial inputs when other systems like the GPS are unable to provide sufficient data in cases similar to when a vehicle passes through a tunnel, or the surroundings have bad weather conditions.[13]

Computer or CPU

The CPU forms the central computer of a driverless car with the ability to link all its functionalities together. High-speed processing of data obtained from various sensors all over the vehicle takes place in the central computer. It is present as a crucial part of the decision-making system and filtering of inputs. It controls the working of automatic throttle, braking, and steering systems with the help of highly sophisticated software by computing necessary outputs for execution. It processes real-time data from the GPS and is connected to the Internet for updates and modification of outputs to improve vehicle performance.[13]

Video Cameras

For the autonomous car to carry out successful application, accurate detection of the environment and surroundings is crucial to have real-world data into consideration to be able to make decisions with the help of the CPU. For capturing real-world information, video cameras are used. ToF and stereo cameras are employed in driverless vehicles. ToF stands for Time of Flight and it helps to measure the speed of light. TOF cameras work by illuminating a scene with a modulated light source and looking at the reflected light. ToF calculates the distance based on the transit time of individual light points. ToF technology is not only useful for acquiring depth data but also for distance measurement. The ToF camera provides two types of statistical values: the intensity value and the object distance from the camera. A stereo camera that simulates two eyes - When it comes to a stereo camera, two digital cameras work together. The image captured by the stereo camera is like the stereo vision of both eyes and the speed, position, distance, etc. of the object. It provides information about many things. Given that the object appears to be pointed in space, the separation of the cameras will result in a difference in the position of the object in the two camera images. The cameras capture the same scene from two distinct perspectives. The software compares and determines the depth of information required for a 3D image. When structured light is added to the stereo solution, the result becomes even more precise.[27]

DECISION-MAKING SYSTEM

The National Highway Transportation Safety Administration (NHTSA) estimates that 94 to 96 % of all motor vehicle collisions occur by human error. Autonomous vehicles (AVs) have emerged as a viable and expanding remedy for collisions caused by driver errors. Research is made to integrate advanced decision-making algorithms that can make safe judgments and drivers acceptable.[28] Collision avoidance is one of the most important aspects of decision-making systems since it is linked to passenger safety. Various CA applications have been deployed in advanced autonomous vehicle systems which help in enhancing driving safety, taking advantage of the rapid growth of environment perception, path planning, and motion control technology. CA consists of three parts including a motion-based system, reinforcement learning, and risk assessment.[29]

DISCUSSION

Autonomous vehicles have the potential to truly modernize society, but they do have some drawbacks. It is nearly impossible to test and validate an autonomous vehicle in a real-world setting before fully implementing it. As a result, there is no comprehensive guarantee that is completely safe and reliable. Given the scarcity of data on the former, there is a research gap between technical aspects and potential market for these vehicles. However, once these difficulties are addressed, this exciting technology has a lot more to offer.

CONCLUSION

Automation is the future, and the autonomous car is a fascinating concept for all researchers worldwide. The driver simply enters the destination, and the autonomous vehicle will navigate itself by calculating and judging all external parameters using various sensors and cameras. The Perception system is responsible for evaluating the vehicle's status and building an internal picture of the surroundings. Autonomous vehicles have been proposed as a promising and growing result to driver error collisions. Research is being conducted to integrate advanced decision-making algorithms capable of making safe and driver-acceptable judgments. The decision-making system oversees functions such as route optimization, control, and obstacle avoidance, among others.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We want to convey our appreciation to Prof. Pavan Rayar for his advice throughout this review paper. He also directed us towards the finalization of the paper's final version.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Q. Chen, Y. Xie, S. Guo, J. Bai, and Q. Shu, "Sensing system of environmental perception technologies for driverless vehicle: A review of state of the art and challenges," *Sensors Actuators, A Phys.*, vol. 319, p. 112566, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.sna.2021.112566.
- [2] N. Faujdar, "Technology of autonomous cars," *Int. J. Latest Trends Eng. Technol.*, no. October, 2017, doi: 10.21172/1.91.11.
- [3] J. Z. Varghese and R. G. Boone, "Overview of Autonomous Vehicle Sensors and Systems," *Int. Conf. Oper. Excell. Serv. Eng.*, pp. 178–191, 2015.
- [4] P. Davidson and A. Spinoulas, "Autonomous Vehicles - What Could This Mean for the Future of Transport?," *AITPM Natl. Conf.*, pp. 1–19, 2015.
- [5] L. T., "Autonomous Vehicle Implementation Predictions: Implications for Transport Planning," *Transp. Res. Board Annu. Meet.*, vol. 42, no. 5 June 2020, pp. 1–39, 2020, [Online]. Available: <https://www.vtpi.org/avip.pdf>
- [6] R. Ayala and T. K. Mohd, "Sensors in Autonomous Vehicles: A Survey," *J. Auton. Veh. Syst.*, vol. 1, no. 3, 2021, doi: 10.1115/1.4052991.
- [7] "SAE International." <https://www.sae.org/> (accessed Aug. 10, 2022).
- [8] T. Inagaki and T. B. Sheridan, "A critique of the SAE conditional driving automation definition, and analyses of options for improvement," *Cogn. Technol. Work*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 569–578, 2019, doi: 10.1007/s10111-018-0471-5.
- [9] F. Novakazi, M. Johansson, H. Strömberg, and M. A. Karlsson, "Levels of What? Investigating Drivers' Understanding of Different Levels of Automation in Vehicles," *J. Cogn. Eng. Decis. Mak.*, vol. 15, no. 2–3, pp. 116–132, 2021, doi: 10.1177/15553434211009024.
- [10] A. C. Serban, E. Poll, and J. Visser, "A Standard Driven Software Architecture for Fully Autonomous Vehicles," *Proc. - 2018 IEEE 15th Int. Conf. Softw. Archit. Companion, ICSA-C 2018*, vol. 00, no. 0, pp. 120–127, 2018, doi: 10.1109/ICSA-C.2018.00040.
- [11] D. K. Killinger, "Lidar (light detection and ranging)," *Laser Spectrosc. Sens. Fundam. Tech. Appl.*, pp. 292–312, Jan. 2014, doi: 10.1533/9780857098733.2.292.
- [12] M. Taveniku, "Introduction to radar processing," *Doktorsavhandlingar vid Chalmers Tek. Hogsk.*, no. 1336, pp. 125–131, 1997.
- [13] J. Ondruš, E. Kolla, P. Vertaľ, and Ž. Šarić, "How Do Autonomous Cars Work?," *Transp. Res. Procedia*, vol. 44, no. 2019, pp. 226–233, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.trpro.2020.02.049.
- [14] H. A. Ignatious, H. El Sayed, and M. Khan, "An overview of sensors in Autonomous Vehicles," *Procedia Comput. Sci.*, vol. 198, no. 2021, pp. 736–741, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2021.12.315.
- [15] S. E. Li et al., "Kalman filter-based tracking of moving objects using linear ultrasonic sensor array for road vehicles," *Mech. Syst. Signal Process.*, vol. 98, pp. 173–189, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.ymssp.2017.04.041.
- [16] M. Noll, P. M. Knoll, and P. Rapps, "Ultrasonic sensor for reverse driving applications," *Sensors Actuators A Phys.*, vol. 31, no. 1–3, pp. 51–53, 1992, doi: 10.1016/0924-4247(92)80079-I.
- [17] J. Zhao, H. Xu, H. Liu, J. Wu, Y. Zheng, and D. Wu, "Detection and tracking of pedestrians and vehicles using roadside LiDAR sensors," *Transp. Res. Part C Emerg. Technol.*, vol. 100, no. January, pp. 68–87, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.trc.2019.01.007.
- [18] J. Hecht, "Lidar for Self-Driving Cars," no. January, pp. 26–33, 2018.
- [19] A. Brun, D. A. Cucci, and J. Skaloud, "Lidar point-to-point correspondences for rigorous registration of kinematic scanning in dynamic networks," *ISPRS J. Photogramm. Remote Sens.*, vol. 189, pp. 185–200, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.1016/J.ISPRSJPRS.2022.04.027.
- [20] O. Sahin, R. V. Nezafat, and M. Cetin, "Methods for classification of truck trailers using side-fire light detection and ranging (LiDAR) Data," *J. Intell. Transp. Syst. Technol. Planning, Oper.*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 1–13, 2021, doi: 10.1080/15472450.2020.1733999.
- [21] Y. Zein, M. Darwiche, and O. Mokhiamar, "GPS tracking system for autonomous vehicles," *Alexandria Eng. J.*, vol. 57, no. 4, pp. 3127–3137, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.aej.2017.12.002.
- [22] U. Sewwandi, "Use of GPS Navigation For Driverless Cars," no. January 2020, 2020.
- [23] H. Lee, H. Chae, and K. Yi, "A Geometric Model based 2D LiDAR/Radar Sensor Fusion for Tracking Surrounding Vehicles," *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 52, no. 8, pp. 277–282, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2019.08.060.
- [24] "The Radar Technology Behind Autonomous Vehicles - Electrical Engineering News and Products." <https://www.eeworldonline.com/the-radar-technology-behind-autonomous-vehicles/> (accessed Aug. 10, 2022).

- [25] A. P. Lakshminarayanan, H. C. Kumawat, and A. B. Raj, "Moving target detection in foliage environment using FMCW Radar," *Proc. 5th Int. Conf. Commun. Electron. Syst. ICCES 2020*, vol. 5, no. Icces, pp. 418–421, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ICCES48766.2020.09138095.
- [26] N. Ahmad, R. A. R. Ghazilla, N. M. Khairi, and V. Kasi, "Reviews on Various Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) Sensor Applications," *Int. J. Signal Process. Syst.*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 256–262, 2013, doi: 10.12720/ijsp.1.2.256-262.
- [27] L. Li, "Time-of-Flight Camera—An Introduction," *Texas Instruments - Tech. White Pap.*, no. January, p. 10, 2014.
- [28] Z. Yu, W. Chen, and C. Zhu, "Design of Unmanned Park Vehicle Decision-making System Based on Uncertainty Information," *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 51, no. 31, pp. 924–929, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1016/J.IFACOL.2018.10.079.
- [29] N. Gallardo, N. Gamez, P. Rad, and M. Jamshidi, "Autonomous decision making for a driver-less car," *2017 12th Syst. Syst. Eng. Conf. SoSE 2017*, 2017, doi: 10.1109/SYSOSE.2017.7994953.

